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AN ASSESSMENT OF GROWTH PATTERNS OF LIFE INSURANCE SECTOR IN INDIA

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ABSTRACT

It is more than 15 years since insurance sector was liberalised in India and the life insurance industry has seen transitioned from super normal growth to steady growth. This paper proposed to trace the more recent growth pattern of the insurance sector in the light of selected variables that includes total premium, first year and renewal premium, number of agents, offices, commissions, claim settlement ratio, new products, capital, assets managed and profits from 2008-2015. Also, it analyses which variables are closely related to total premium and if there is any difference in the performance of public and private life insurers. Till 2010, the variables selected reflect a strong growth pattern followed by a dull phase for the industry. Post 2013-14, the industry is witnessing a revival of growth. Most of the selected variables are significantly related to premium and there is a significant difference in the performance of private life insurers and LIC.

Keywords: Growth, performance, life insurance industry, premium, LIC

1. Introduction:

Insurance sector was opened up for private and foreign participation in 1999 on the basis of the recommendations of the high powered committee led by Mr. R. N. Malhotra, with an intention of professionalising the insurance sector. Insurance Regulatory Development Authority was also formed considering the objectives of promoting competition, increasing customer satisfaction, increasing consumer choice and lowering premiums all the while ensuring the financial security of the market.

As on March 2015, there are 23 private players operating in the industry. From the economy perspective, the insurance sector plays a vital role in mobilizing the savings of the household, private and public sector and channelizes funds for long term infrastructure projects. It is said that the estimates of funds required for India's infrastructure sector in the 12th Plan period is

Rs. 65,79,463 crores (Working sub-group on infrastructure, Planning commission) . Life insurance premiums has contributed over Rs. 155,026 crores in 2014 and Rs. 174,512 crores in 2015 in housing and infrastructure investments. A further addition of Rs. 24,544 crores in 2014 and Rs. 27,277 crores in 2015 has come from non life insurers. IRDA has also mandated to life insurers that 15% of their investments be made in infrastructure to further strengthen the infrastructure sector. Insurance companies play an important role by providing a cover against uncertainties that would otherwise seriously impact individuals and business enterprises. On an average claims settled by life insurers grew by 17% between 2010 and 2015 (Handbook on Indian Insurance Statistics, 2013-14). In 2014-15 alone claims of over 851,000 policies amounting to Rs. 11,789 crores have been paid by the life insurance industry. In the general insurance sector, Rs. 55,232 crores have been settled against claims. It is well known that insurance sector creates huge employment opportunities. Sinha (2005) underscores the mutual dependence of capital markets and insurance sector by way of bi-directional movement of funds and expertise. FDI inflows to the sector has been Rs.6,147 crores as on March, 2015 and all the above point to the contribution of insurance sector to economic development.

The major strengths of the insurance sector lies in the increasing awareness of insurance as a result of aggressive marketing strategies adopted by the insurance players, intense competition bringing in innovative and diversified products, bringing down the premiums of insurance products, a gradual increase in the working population and the trend towards nuclear families and IRDA regulations unleashing on the players to bring in professionalization, capital adequacy, transparency, solvency, etc. However, the challenges faced are competition-induced pressure on premium rates, falling growth in premiums collected, lack of transparency on financial and operational data, lack of adequate trained personnel /professionals in the insurance companies and the need for additional capital. In this context, this paper sets forth to track the growth in the insurance sector in India after the privatisation from the perspective of selected variables.

This paper proposes to study the insurance sector using selected variables like premium collected, new products introduced, insurance claims settlement, no. of branches or offices operating, commission paid to the agents, capital invested, assets managed and profitability. The rest of the paper is organised in the following manner: section 2 deals with literature review, section 3 highlights the objectives, section 4 presents data and the Research

methodology, section 5 contains analysis and interpretation, section 6 covers findings and discussion and the final section deals with concluding remarks.

2. Literature Review:

There has been many attempts to study the growth of insurance sector, the determinants of growth and the relationship between growth of insurance sector and economic development in India and in other countries.

Raji Reddy & Suresh Chandra (2011) have traced the growth in the insurance sector after a decade of announcement of liberalisation, the growth of private sector of the competition and challenges that lay ahead in the future. They have mentioned about the focus of insurance companies on ULIP products, decline in the market share of LIC to 70%, and the problems like increased lapsation rates, especially in private insurance segment, dearth of highly qualified distributors, need for better risk and fraud management, etc. Sonika and Priti (2011) analysed life insurers in terms of total number of offices, number of individual agents, number of products and riders, life insurance business and premium income, lapse / forfeiture ratio and settlement of death claims and found differing performance in LIC and private insurance companies. Venkatesh (2013) in his study of trend analysis of insurance sector in India underlines that though Indian insurance sector is growing, compared to the growth of developed countries, growth in Indian insurance, both life and non-life is slower and suggests that proper strategies may be implemented to increase the pace of growth of insurance sector in India. Hymavathi (2013) attempts to study the financial performance of , both private and public players of the insurance industry in the light of liberalisation, using a few important ratios like total assets to earned premium, investment income to earned premium, investment income to total earnings ratio, current ratio and her results confirm the alternate hypothesis of significant growth in all the ratios considered for private and public insurers. Bhavani & Veena (2013) discussed the growth and development of Indian Life insurance industry considering the fresh business premium, Total business premium, Market share and Claims Settlement Ratio of LIC (Public) and Private insurance companies. This paper also identifies a list of reasons for high claim repudiation / rejection ratio by life insurance companies. Leepsa and Sabat Kumar Digal (2015), using percentage analysis and growth trends, test whether there is any difference in the performance of identified Key Performance Indicators of the public and private insurers. Their study concludes that both in life and non-life insurance, public insurer fares better, perhaps because of their dominance in the market and reliability as perceived by customers. Arif (2015) in his study on life insurance industry and

its trends and patterns revealed that there has been a great increase in penetration, density, capital inflows, number of products and number of offices. However, the need for innovative strategies to serve untapped market is highlighted.

The present study considers a comprehensive list of variables and presents the growth pattern of Indian Life Insurance sector.

3. Objectives:

- To identify growth patterns of selected variables of the insurance sector
- To measure the growth and its trend of the relevant variables of insurance sector
- To understand the relationship between the growth of the insurance sector and the selected variables
- To find the difference in the performance of public life insurer and private life insurers.

The variables considered for this study are as follows:

- Total premium collected by the life insurance sector,
- First Year Premium,
- Renewal Premium,
- Number of new products introduced,
- No. of branches,
- No. of agents,
- Commission expenses,
- Claim settlement ratio,
- Capital invested,
- Assets under management and
- Profitability.

4. Data and Research Methodology:

Secondary data has been taken for this study and the source of data is the annual reports of IRDA for various years and the Handbook on Indian Insurance Statistics, 2013-2014 published by IRDA. The period of the study has been chosen as from 2007-08 to 2014-15.

The following hypotheses have been framed for this study:

- There is significant relationship between total premium (representing growth of insurance sector) and the other variables selected.
- There is significant difference in the performance of public and private life insurers during the period of this study.

The methodology used is percentage analysis, Compounded Annual Growth Rate, Trend analysis and Correlation and t-test.

5. Analysis and Interpretation:

Insurance Penetration calculated as the Total premiums collected by Gross Domestic Product and Insurance Density calculated as Total premium collected by the population are the commonly used measures to capture the growth of insurance industry in an economy. Table 1 presents the insurance penetration and insurance density of Indian life insurance sector for the study period. From the table, it is revealed that though until 2010 the ratio of penetration and density have increased, after 2010, the values have dropped with the exception that there is a small increase in the life insurance density in 2014. It should be noted that compared to World's average, Insurance penetration (except in 2008, 2009 and 2010) and Insurance density of India are very less (IRDA Handbook, 2014).

Table 1: Insurance penetration and density for Indian Life insurance sector

Year	Insurance Penetration (%)	Insurance Density (USD)
2008	4.0	41.2
2009	4.6	47.7
2010	4.4	55.7
2011	3.4	49.0
2012	3.17	42.7
2013	3.1	41.0
2014	2.6	44.0

Table 2: Growth in life premiums underwritten by Insurers in Rs. Cr

Year	LIC	Private	Total Premium	Growth (%)	Trend (%)
2007-08	149790	51561	201351		100
2008-09	157288	64497	221785	10	110
2009-10	186077	79370	265447	20	132
2010-11	203473	88165	291638	10	145
2011-12	202889	84183	287072	-2	143
2012-13	208803	78398	287201	0	143
2013-14	236942	77341	314283	9	156
2014-15	239668	88433	328101	4	163
CAGR % (08 - 15)			6		

Table 2 gives the details of premium collected by life insurance companies, both LIC and private players during the study period. It is understood that the insurance premium had increased till 2011 and then declined. IRDA tightened norms in 2010 for unit linked products, the premium of which declined drastically after 2010. Fall in the First year premium after 2011 is also considered as a reason for negative growth in insurance premium collected in 2012. Between 2008 and 2015, the trend value indicates that the premium collection has grown by 63% and compounded annual growth rate (CAGR) is a mere 6%.

Table 3 briefs about the First year and Renewal premium collected by the life insurance companies in India. It is given from the data that there is almost an increasing trend in all the years in the renewal premiums of both LIC and private (except in 2012-13). However, First Year premiums share a different story.

Table 3. First Year and Renewal premium of Life insurers in Rs. Cr.

Year	LIC		Private		Total		Growth (%)		Trend (%)	
	FYP	RP	FYP	RP	FYP	RP	FYP	RP	FYP	RP
2007-08	59997	89793	33716	17845	93713	107639			100	100
2008-09	53179	104109	34152	30345	87331	134454	-7	25	93	125
2009-10	71522	114555	38372	40998	109894	155553	26	16	117	145
2010-11	87012	116461	39386	48763	126398	165240	15	6	135	154
2011-12	81862	121027	32080	52103	113942	173130	-10	5	122	161
2012-13	76612	132192	30750	47649	107361	179840	-6	4	115	167
2013-14	90809	146134	29511	47830	120320	193964	12	8	128	180
2014-15	78508	161160	34820	53613	113328	214773	-6	8	121	200
CAGR % (08 - 15)					2	9				

Note: FYP - First Year Premium, RP - Renewal Premium

Table 4: Number of New products launched by life insurance companies

Year	LIC	Private	Total	Growth (%)	Trend (%)
2007-08	6	179	185		100
2008-09	9	202	211	14	114
2009-10	9	357	366	73	198
2010-11	6	246	252	-31	136
2011-12	4	141	145	-42	78
2012-13	5	112	117	-19	63
2013-14	20	481	501	328	271
2014-15	10	132	142	-72	77
CAGR % (08 - 15)			-3		

Table 4 briefs about the number of new life insurance products introduced by insurance companies between 2008-2015. In 2013-14, highest number of products have been introduced by both LIC and private players. However, contrastingly a sharp fall in the new products is seen in 2012-13 for the industry. Again in 2014-15, lesser number of new products have been introduced than in 2013-14. Both the trend and CAGR (-3%) show negative growth in the number of new products between 2008 and 2015.

Table 5 details about the number of branches operated by life insurers region-wise. LIC has constantly increased their branch network, however private players show a different story with number of branches increasing in the first couple of years followed by reduction in number of branches for all the years. Total number of branches increased in 2008-09 after which there is a constant fall in the number of branches. There is a mixed trend in the number of branches operated in metros and urban areas, however, branches operating in other areas, comprising rural areas has been constantly reducing for private players. The private players are evaluating and re-evaluating the cost-benefit of operating rural branches. The CAGR rate has been a marginal 3% growth between 2008 and 2015 and trend value shows an increasing of number of branches by 24% between 2008 and 2015.

Table 5: Region-wise distribution of Life insurers (in No.s)

Year	LIC			Private			Total	Growth (%)	Trend (%)
	Metro	Urban	Others	Metro	Urban	Others			
2007-08	311	468	1743	628	1169	4594	8913		100
2008-09	338	529	2163	927	1594	6264	11815	33	133
2009-10	347	550	2353	897	1555	6316	12018	1.7	135
2010-11	363	560	2448	769	1428	5977	11545	-3.9	130
2011-12	365	563	2527	741	1393	5578	11167	-3.3	125
2012-13	365	614	2544	703	1519	4537	10285	-7.9	115
2013-14	365	617	3850	676	1926	3591	11032	7.3	124
2014-15	365	622	3877	705	1867	3584	11033	0.0	124
CAGR % (08 -15)							3		

Table 6: Commission expenses and commission ratio of life insurers

Year	Commission (Rs. Cr.)					Commission ratio (%)			
	LIC	Private	Total	Growth (%)	Trend (%)	LIC	Private	Total	Trend (%)
2007-08	9615	5090	14704		100	6.4	9.9	7.3	100
2008-09	10055	5478	15533	6	106	6.4	8.5	7.0	96
2009-10	12110	5944	18054	16	123	6.5	7.5	6.8	93
2010-11	13309	4972	18280	1	124	6.5	5.6	6.3	86
2011-12	14036	4463	18499	1	126	6.9	5.3	6.4	88
2012-13	14790	4471	19261	4	131	7.1	5.7	6.7	92
2013-14	16763	4083	20846	8	142	7.1	5.3	6.6	91
2014-15	15118	4343	19461	-7	132	6.3	4.9	5.9	81
CAGR % (08 - 15)			4					-3	

Table 6 deals with the commission expenses and commission ratio of life insurers between 2008 and 2015. There is evidently a huge increase in the payout of commission in 2008-09 compared to 2007-08, i.e, the commission payout has grown by 16% over the previous year. In the next two consecutive years (2011-12), however, there is a mere 1% growth in commission paid by the insurers. This is in tandem with the premium collected by life insurers which shows a declining growth rate of 10% and -2% in these two years. From 2012-13, the premium collections exhibit a gradual increase and accordingly the commission paid to individual and corporate agents surges to 4% and higher. The CAGR of the commission expenses in 4% , lesser by 2% of the CAGR of premium collected by life insurance companies. The trend analysis shows that the commission paid to agents has grown to 132%

of what was given in 2007-08. Commission ratio (commission expenses by premiums collected) shows has registered a negative growth in 5 out of 7 years, a negative CAGR, i.e - 3% . Similarly, trend ratio in 2014-15 is 81% of what was calculated in 2007-08. This indicates as a percentage of premiums, there is a decline of ratio of commissions paid. The intervening role of IRDA in 2010 in tightening norms for commission paid by insurers to agents has to be mentioned in this context. It is also to be noted that IRDA has been said to come out with a draft in 2015 planning to rationalise the commission structure of agents again, which is yet to become notified.

Table 7. Number of Individual and Corporate agents of Life insurance companies

Year	Individual agents			Corporate agents			Total agents	Growth (%)	Trend (%)
	LIC	Private	Total	LIC	Private	Total			
2007-08	1193744	1292236	2485980	345	2070	2415	2488395		100
2008-09	1344856	1538358	2883214	415	2091	2506	2885720	16	116
2009-10	1402807	1495846	2898653	510	2420	2930	2901583	1	117
2010-11	1337064	1244776	2581840	295	1870	2165	2584005	-11	104
2011-12	1278234	1016528	2294762	240	642	882	2295644	-11	92
2012-13	1172983	949774	2122757	207	532	739	2123496	-8	85
2013-14	1195916	992584	2188500	149	540	689	2189189	-3	88
2014-15	1163604	904303	2067907	142	361	503	2068410	6	83
CAGR % (08 - 15)	0	-4	-2	-11	-20	-18	-2		

Table 7 exhibits the details of number of individual and corporate agents of LIC, private players and the industry. Between 2008 and 2015, number of LIC individual agents has increased from 1193744 to 1402807 and then fell to 1163604. In case of private insurers, the count was 1292236 in 2008, whereas increased to 1538358 in the next year and later decreased gradually to 904303 in 2015. The number of corporate agents of LIC and private players decreased from 345 and 2070 in 2008 to 142 and 361 respectively in 2015. The CAGR for LIC's individual agents is nearly 0%, whereas the CAGR for LIC's corporate agents and for private insurers' individual and corporate agents were -11%, -4% and -2% respectively. The total number of agents of LIC and private players together reduced from

2488395 to 2068410 with a CAGR of -2%, which is also highlighted in trend values of 83% in 2015 compared to 100% in 2008.

Table 8. Claim settlement ratio of life insurers in %

Year	Individual		Group		Total Settlement ratio		Total Settlement ratio		
	LIC	Private	LIC	Private	Individual	Group	LIC	Private	Total
2007-08	96.71	78.93	99.88	84.43	95.86	97.85	97.36	81.34	89.35
2008-09	95.48	82.26	99.76	92.51	94.46	98.63	96.65	86.92	91.79
2009-10	96.54	84.88	99.80	96.80	95.24	98.90	97.33	91.11	94.22
2010-11	97.03	86.05	99.66	93.33	95.58	96.73	97.66	90.73	94.20
2011-12	97.42	89.34	99.64	90.03	96.26	95.86	97.98	89.73	93.85
2012-13	97.73	88.65	99.54	87.79	96.41	95.69	98.18	88.23	93.20
2013-14	98.14	88.31	99.65	90.45	96.75	96.22	98.54	89.51	94.02
2014-15	98.19	89.40	99.64	91.20	96.97	96.15	98.58	90.51	94.54

Table 8 illustrates the claim settlement ratio of life insurance companies. It is a known fact the settlement ratio of LIC is better than private players. The claim settlement ratio has been 96.71% in 2008 for LIC and 78.93% for private companies taking individual policies into consideration. For group policies, the ratio is better at 99.88% for LIC and 84.43% for others in 2008. Over the years the companies have worked hard to improve the claim settlement ratio and the values in 2015 have improved to 98.19% and 89.40% (LIC and private for individual policies) and 99.64% and 91.20% (LIC and private for group policies). Total settlement ratio for individual and group policies (considering both LIC and private companies), the claim settlement ratio stands at 95.86% and 97.85% respectively in 2008 and 96.97% and 96.15% respectively in 2015. Similarly total settlement ratio for LIC and private players (considering both individual and group policies), the claim settlement ratio stands at 97.36% and 81.34% respectively in 2008 and 98.58% and 90.51% respectively in 2015. The total average claim settlement ratio of the industry has progressed from 89.35% to 94.54% between 2008 and 2015.

Table 9. Capital employed by life insurance companies (Rs. Cr.)

Year	LIC	Private	Total	Growth (%)	Trend (%)
2007-08	5	12291	12296		100
2008-09	5	18248	18253	48	148
2009-10	5	21015	21020	15	171
2010-11	5	23657	23662	13	192
2011-12	100	24832	24932	5	203
2012-13	100	25419	25519	2	208
2013-14	100	25839	25939	2	211
2014-15	100	26144	26244	1	213
CAGR % (08 - 15)	45	10	10		

In terms of capital employed, LIC had once increased the capital from Rs. 5 cr. to Rs.100 cr in 2011-12 to fulfil IRDA's norms of minimum capital requirements for life insurance companies. However, in the segment of private players capital as well as the number of companies have increased. From Rs. 12291 cr in 2008, the capital employed by private players rose to Rs. 26144 cr in 2015. In the initial the growth rate in capital is higher than the last few years. However, there is going to be news in this aspect from private players following the increase in FDI limit to 49% in insurance companies. Again, the companies have also been permitted to raise funds from the capital market through share issues by the regulator. The trend % has increased to 213% in 2015 from 2008 and the CAGR is calculated as 45% for LIC and 10% for private players and industry as a whole.

Table 10. Assets under management of life insurance companies (Rs Cr.)

Year	LIC	Private	Total	Growth (%)	Trend (%)
2007-08	678403	87567	765970		100
2008-09	799593	116772	916365	20	120
2009-10	992331	220127	1212458	32	158
2010-11	1148589	281528	1430117	18	187
2011-12	1269070	312188	1581258	11	206
2012-13	1402991	341902	1744893	10	228
2013-14	1574296	383169	1957465	12	256
2014-15	1786313	461210	2247522	15	293
CAGR % (08 - 15)	13	23	14		

Table 10 contains the details of the assets under management of insurance companies. There is a steady growth in the assets of insurance companies (LIC and private) during the study

period. The assets of LIC, private was Rs. 678403 cr. and Rs. 87567 cr. in 2008 and Rs. 1786313 cr. and Rs. 461210 cr. in 2015. The growth rate of assets over previous year for the industry has been in the range of 10% to 32%. The CAGR of industry is 14% for assets under management and trend value is 293% in 2015 against 100% in 2008.

Table 11. Profitability of life insurance companies (Rs. Cr.)

Year	LIC	Private	Total	Growth (%)	Trend (%)
2007-08	845	-4257	-3413		-100
2008-09	957	-5840	-4883	-43	-143
2009-10	1061	-2050	-989	80	-29
2010-11	1172	1485	2657	369	78
2011-12	1313	4660	5974	125	175
2012-13	1438	5511	6948	16	204
2013-14	1657	5931	7588	9	222
2014-15	1824	5787	7611	0	223
CAGR % (08 - 15)	10	4	11		

In terms of profitability, the companies have recorded huge growth during the study period. LIC 's profit has been on the increase throughout, whereas private companies, initially recorded heavy loss to the tune of Rs. 4257 cr, but turned profitable in the midway and profits reported for 2015 by private players is Rs. 5787 cr. The profits of the industry in 2015 is Rs. 7611 cr. The growth rate was highest in 2010-11 over 2009-10 and the trend % increased from -100% (loss) to 223% between 2008 and 2015.

Table 12: Correlation coefficient values of Total premium and other study variables

Variables	LIC*	Private*	Industry*
Total Premium	1.00	1.00	1.00
FYP	0.85	0.22	0.83
RP	0.96	0.96	0.98
New Products	0.46	0.03	-0.88
Offices	0.93	0.07	0.35
Commission	0.97	-0.35	0.95
Agents	-0.42	-0.48	-0.74
Claim settlement ratio	0.88	0.93	0.89
Capital employed	0.78	0.90	0.95
AUM	0.98	0.81	0.96
Profit	0.96	0.72	0.91

* 5% critical value for 6 d.f= 0.7067 (N=8)

The relationship between total premium and the other study variables for LIC, private insurers and the total industry is dealt in the next part. This gives an idea about which variables are related to premium growth. Though soon after liberalisation, the penetration level increased for life insurance industry, since 2010, the insurance penetration is on the decline. The understanding of the variables that are related to life insurance premium collected may be helpful to focus on the certain variables that will result in increased premium collections. Table 12 presents the correlation coefficients of Total premium and other variables of LIC, Private life insurers and the industry. From the table, it is learnt that for all the three, Assets under Management, Renewal premium, Claim settlement ratio, Capital employed and Profit have significant relationship with Total premium. It is remarked that assets and profit are calculated after premium collection. However, renewals, claims settlement and capital invested are significant variables that share relationship with premium collected. Apart from this, FYP and Commission significantly related to Total premium for LIC and the industry. This reveals the highlighting role of commission in the life insurance industry. First year premiums sharing relationship with premium tells new policies are being taken by people and more number of lives are covered by insurance policies. Number of Offices is significant to total premium for LIC alone. The geographical reach of LIC and its prominence in total premium collection is explained by this. Number of agents (individual and corporate) and New products are significant and negatively related to total premium for industry alone. This points out that introduction of newer products are not well received by the people. An increase in the number of agents and new products may not necessarily lead to increased premium. Further, in this paper, negative relationship is shown. A closer look at the corresponding tables indicate that industry premium has been growing except 2011-12, and data for new products introduced and number of agents show mixed pattern. Premium is growing in spite of lesser number of new products and agents, which is an observation contradictory to the belief that new products and more agents sell more policies and collect more premium. Hence, it is concluded that for life insurance industry, apart from number of offices, the hypothesis that all other variables are significantly related to the growth of insurance sector, is accepted.

Table 13 explains the difference in the variables taken for the study between LIC and private insurers through t-test. It is understood from the above table that except profit, for all other variables there is significant difference between LIC and private insurance companies for the

variables considered. Therefore, for the past 8 years, the performance of LIC and private insurers in respect of insurance premium, First year collection, renewals, new products,

Table 13. T-test testing significance of difference in variables between LIC and private insurers:

Variables	t-test	P-value
Total Premium	14.31	0.0000
FYP	8.40	0.0000
RP	15.46	0.0000
New Products	-5.09	0.0007
Offices	-6.21	0.0002
Commission	7.85	0.0001
Agents	39.01	0.0000
Claim settlement ratio	8.11	0.0000
Capital employed	-13.06	0.0000
AUM	10.42	0.0000
Profit	-0.08	0.4711

number of offices, agents, commission paid, claim settlement ratio and assets under management are significantly different from each other. However, in terms of profitability of these two segments, there is statistically no significant difference. The hypothesis that there is significant difference in the performance of LIC and private companies is accepted except for profitability.

6. Findings and Discussion:

Insurance penetration reveals a negative growth since 2010 and insurance density has also been negatively growing for 3 consecutive years between 2011 and 2014. Annual growth rate of Premium collections is 6% and growth in the last year is 4%. Comparing with average growth of life premium collection in the emerging markets at 6.9% and in emerging Asia at 9.9% in 2014 (Sigma, 2015), India's performance of life insurance sector cannot be taken as satisfactory. Growth pattern in Renewal premium has been positive for the last 8 years, while mixed pattern of growth is demonstrated in first year premium. From the above paper, it is understood that in the years 2007-08, 2008-09 and 2009-10, the life insurance sector in India registered high year-on-year growth in many aspects like premiums, new products, commission paid, expansion of geographical reach in terms of number of offices, capital

invested, assets managed, profits earned, etc. It is also revealed that all variables selected for study (except new products, number of agents for LIC, and number of offices for industry) are significantly related to premium collected. In case of private players, except First year premium, New products, Number of offices, Commission paid and number of agents, other variables are significantly related to premium collected. The paper also tells that there is significant difference in the values of LIC and private players for all the variables, excluding profitability, during the period of the study. This may mean that the growth of LIC and private players are not the same and follow different paths.

In 2010, many regulations were introduced with an objective to streamline insurance sector and safeguard policyholders interests. Major regulations were introduced like cutting down commissions paid, capping surrender charges and fund management charges, increasing life insurance component, raising lock-in period of life insurance policies, standardising surrender value to be paid, etc. ULIP products which were cash-cows for private and public insurers until 2010 were regulated in terms of the upfront and other commissions taken from the ULIP premium, disseminating information periodically to policy holders about the charges levied from premiums collected, etc.

Recently, the much awaited bill to increase in FDI cap in insurance sector to 49% was also passed. This is expected to bring some relief to the cash starved industry as claimed by the companies. Apart from that, SEBI has also issued guidelines for insurance companies to raise funds through public issue. Increase in capital is expected to enable the companies to reach the untapped segments of the market and drive profitable growth for the companies. IRDA mandates all insurance companies to sell of a portion of policies to the rural masses. This not only increases the penetration, but also the premium collection and thereby, profitability of the insurance sector.

7. Conclusion:

The paper discusses the growth of Indian Insurance sector in terms of selected financial and marketing variables from 2007-08 to 2014-15. Along with this, year-on-year growth, trend analysis and compounded annual growth rate are also presented in this paper. During the first decade of liberalisation, upto 2010, when many insurance companies started, the life insurance industry reported remarkable growth on various parameters like premiums, new products, number of offices, agents, commissions paid, assets managed, capital and profits.

Most of the variables considered in the study are related to total premiums received by the insurance companies. For all the variables but profit earned, it is found that there is significant difference in LIC and private players. IRDA's regulatory interventions, and policyholder-friendly norms are aimed at a fair environment and achieving a stable, and just not rapid growth for insurers. In 2013-14 and thereafter, it is to be noted that life insurance companies are gradually resuming from an episode of de-growth. Given the large Indian population, the insurers have immense potential to enter under penetrated segments and include them into the fold as policyholders and thereby march towards higher levels of growth.

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